

Metal Complexes of Some Model Peptides. Part—I : Complex Formation of Cu(II) with N-Salicyloyl Glycine

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pH-Metric study of the interaction of Cu(II) with N-salicyloyl glycine, *o*-(OH)-C₆H₄CONHCH₂COOH, LH₂, indicated the stepwise formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal:ligand complexes. The phenolic -OH group was not involved in coordination to Cu(II), as its deprotonation occurred only after the completion of formation of the 1:2 complex. Coordination from the N-(peptide) atom occurred only through deprotonation. The stepwise equilibrium constants (K₁' and K₂') of complex formation, stepwise deprotonation constants (k_{2,OH} and k_{1,OH}) of the 1:2 complex, Cu(LH)₂²⁻ ion and successive acid dissociation constants (k_{COOH}, k_{OH} and k_{NH}) of the ligand LH₂ have been determined. The overall stability constants, β_{pqr} of the complexes [Cu_pH_qL_r^{+2p+q-2r}] have been calculated. The pK₁', pK₂', pK_{2,OH}', pK_{1,OH}', pK_{COOH}', pK_{OH}', pK_{NH}', log β₁₁₁, log β₁₂₂, log β₁₁₂ and log β₁₀₂ values have been found to be 6.54 ± 0.04, 6.76 ± 0.04, 8.68 ± 0.04, 9.46 ± 0.04, 4.26 ± 0.02, 9.12 ± 0.04, 12.88 ± 0.01, 6.84 ± 0.04, 13.46 ± 0.04, 17.66 ± 0.04 and 21.08 ± 0.04, respectively at 30 ± 0.5° in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol at a constant ionic strength μ = 0.2 M (NaClO₄). Trends in the pK_{OH} values of the free and of the complexed ligand and the equilibrium distribution of the complex species have been discussed.

THE model peptide ligand N-salicyloyl glycine, *o*-(OH)C₆H₄CONHCH₂COOH, (LH₂) is widely used as an antiinflammatory drug¹. In the present work its interaction with Cu(II) ion has been followed *pH*-metrically at 30 ± 0.5° in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol medium at a constant ionic strength, μ = 0.2 M (NaClO₄). The study indicated the stepwise formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal:ligand complexes in which coordination to the metal was provided by the carboxylic oxygen and the N-(peptide) atom of the ligand. Coordination of the N-(peptide) atom occurred only on deprotonation²⁻¹². Deprotonation of the phenolic-(OH) group occurred only after the completion of the formation of the 1:2 complex suggesting non-involvement of this group in coordination.

Experimental

The ligand, N-salicyloyl glycine, was prepared and purified by the reported procedure¹⁴. All other reagents were either of A. R. quality or properly purified and their solutions were made in double distilled CO₂ free water and purified and dry ethanol¹⁵.

pH-Metric titrations of 50 ml solutions of the following compositions:

- (i) 0.02 M HClO₄,
- (ii) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.01 M LH₂,
- (iii) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.01 M LH₂ + 0.001 M Cu(ClO₄)₂,
- (iii) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.01 M LH₂ + 0.002 M Cu(ClO₄)₂

were performed in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol medium with a standard NaOH solution in the same solvent medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, μ = 0.2 M by adding requisite amounts of NaClO₄, at 30 ± 0.5°. *pH* measurements were made with a Cambridge *pH*-meter (Portable type) having a glass electrode of 1-13 *pH* range and a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar 2 M NaNO₃ bridge. The meter was calibrated using standard 0.02 M HClO₄, phthalate buffer and borate buffer solutions with appropriate temperature corrections.

Titration curves, *pH* vs volume of alkali, were drawn (Fig. 1) and the necessary concentration variables e.g., $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$, $\bar{n}_{OH}$, pLH_2 etc. were calculated following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁶.

Results and Discussion

Stepwise acid dissociation of N-salicyloyl glycine (LH₂):

Consumption of more than two equivalents of alkali per mole of the ligand N-salicyloyl glycine in the *pH* range 2.5 to 12.5 in the titration of solution (ii) indicated three successive steps of its acid dissociation as represented by the equilibria (1)-(3).

where k_{COOH} , k_{OH} and k_{NH} are the successive acid dissociation constants. The possibility of enolisation, $-CONH- \rightleftharpoons C(OH)=N-$, of the peptide

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves. Initial volume 50 ml in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol, ionic strength, $\mu=0.2(\text{NaClO}_4)$ in each case.

- Curve 1 : 0.02 M HClO_4 .
 - Curve 2 : 0.02 M HClO_4 + 0.01 M N-salicyloylglycine, (LH_2).
 - Curve 3 : 0.02 M HClO_4 + 0.01 M N-salicyloylglycine, (LH_2) + 0.001 M $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$.
 - Curve 4 : 0.02 M HClO_4 + 0.01 M N-salicyloylglycine, (LH_2) + 0.002 M $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$.
- Titrant : 0.125 M NaOH ($\mu=0.2$)

group could not, however, be ruled out. The plot of $\bar{n}_H$ (the average number of protons bound to the ligand ion, L^{2-}) against pH showed that the steps (1), (2) and (3) were all independent of one another and therefore, the constants k_{COOH} , k_{OH} and k_{NH} were evaluated by curve fitting method for one step system and also by the method of linear plots. The refined pK_{COOH} , pK_{OH} and pK_{NH} values are given in Table 1.

Complexation of Cu(II) with N-salicyloyl glycine :

The nature of the pH titration curves of the ligand solution in the presence of Cu(II) (curves 3, 4 ; Fig. 1) indicated the liberation of four equivalents of acid per gm ion of the metal in the pH range from 2.5 to 7.0 and two further equivalents of acid in the pH range from 7.75 to 10.50. The buffer region corresponding to the liberation of the latter two equivalents of acid was practically the same as that was corresponding to the deprotonation of the -OH group of the ligand in the absence of Cu(II). Therefore, the liberation of four equivalents of acid at the early stages of the reaction below pH 7

is clearly due to coordination of -COOH group and N-(peptide)¹⁷ atom to Cu(II) each with deprotonation, ultimately leading to the formation of the 1 : 2 complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2]^{2-}$, according to the reactions (4) and (5), and these were followed by the deprotonation of the phenolic-OH groups not coordinated to the metal in the pH range 7.75-10.50 in a stepwise manner according to the reactions (6) and (7) :

where K'_1 , K'_2 , k_{2OH} and k_{1OH} are the equilibrium constants of the respective complexation and deprotonation steps and LH_2^{2-} stands for the ligand ion $o-(\text{HO})C_6H_4CONCH_2COO^{2-}$.

The presence of the phenolic-OH group in the isolated compound $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was indicated by the appearance of an intense violet colour on addition of neutral FeCl_3 to its aqueous ethanolic solution and also by the appearance of a broad ir band in the region $3500\text{-}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The green compound $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained by treating a solution of the ligand LH_2 (0.1 mole) with equimolar amount of copper sulphate solution in hot water and adjusting the pH to ≈ 4.5 . It was recrystallised from ethanol, air dried and analysed. Found : Cu, 21.86 ; N, 4.29 ; loss at 105° , 12.17%. Calcd. for $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Cu, 21.72 ; N, 4.78 ; H_2O , 12.31%. Metal : ligand ratios in the complexes formed in solution were also determined spectrophotometrically at 610 nm by the method of continuous variation, under the same experimental conditions at two different pH values, viz., at $\text{pH}=7$ where $\bar{n} \approx 4$ and at $\text{pH} \approx 11$ where $\bar{n}_{OH} \approx 0$. At both the pH values the maximum absorption corresponded to the 1 : 2 metal : ligand ratio. Therefore, liberation of acid at pH values higher than 7 was due to deprotonation of the 1 : 2 complex, and not due to the formation of higher complexes. The pK'_1 and pK'_2 values were evaluated from the plot of $\bar{n}$, the average number of protons liberated due to reactions (4) and (5), against $p\text{LH}_2 - 2\text{pH}$ and were refined by various computational methods¹⁷. The $\bar{n}$ values were calculated using portion of the titration curves (3 and 4 ; Fig. 1) from pH 2.5 to pH 7.0 and assuming all the Cu(II) ions in the forms of Cu^{2+} , $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2^{2-}$ ion, in this pH range. The values of pK_{2OH} and pK_{1OH} were evaluated from the plot of $\bar{n}_{OH}$, the average number of protons bound to the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2^{2-}]$ ion against pH, assuming all the Cu(II) ions in the forms of the complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2^{2-}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{LH})^{2-}$

TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND AND Cu(II)-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, $\mu = 0.2$ (NaClO₄) 50% (v/v) WATER-ETHANOL

$pK_{\text{COOH}} = 4.26 \pm 0.02$	$pK'_1 = 6.54 \pm 0.04$	$\log \beta_{111} = 6.84 \pm 0.04$
$pK_{\text{OH}} = 9.12 \pm 0.04$	$pK'_2 = 6.76 \pm 0.04$	$\log \beta_{122} = 13.46 \pm 0.04$
$pK_{\text{NH}} = 12.88 \pm 0.04$	$pK_{2\text{OH}} = 8.68 \pm 0.04$	$\log \beta_{112} = 17.66 \pm 0.04$
	$pK_{1\text{OH}} = 9.46 \pm 0.04$	$\log \beta_{102} = 21.08 \pm 0.04$

and $\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2^{4-}$ in the pH range from 7.75 to 10.5, and were refined as before¹⁷.

The overall stability constants^{18,19} of these Cu(II) complexes of the general formula $[\text{Cu}_p\text{H}_q\text{L}_r^{(2p+q-rx)}]^{+}$ as defined by the relation :

$$\beta_{\text{pur}} = \frac{[\text{Cu}_p\text{H}_q\text{L}_r^{(2p+q-rx)}]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]^p[\text{H}^+]^q[\text{L}^{2-}]^r} \quad \dots (8)$$

were calculated using $p=1$ and $x=3$. Concordance of duplicate titrations [soln (iii) and (iv)] using two different concentrations of the metal ion ruled out the possibility of formation of any polynuclear complex under the condition studied. The overall stability constants β_{111} , β_{122} , β_{112} and β_{102} have been evaluated from the relations :

$$\beta_{111} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})^0]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}][(\text{LH})^{2-}]} = \frac{K'_1}{K_{\text{COOH}}K_{\text{OH}}} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\beta_{122} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2^{2-}]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}][(\text{LH})^{2-}]^2} = \frac{K'_1 K'_2}{(K_{\text{COOH}}K_{\text{OH}})^2} \quad \dots (10)$$

$$\beta_{112} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})(\text{L})^{2-}]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}][\text{LH}^{2-}][\text{L}^{2-}]} = \frac{\beta_{122} \cdot K_{2\text{OH}}}{K_{\text{NH}}} \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\beta_{102} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2^{4-}]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}][\text{L}^{2-}]^2} = \frac{\beta_{112} \cdot K_{1\text{OH}}}{K_{\text{NH}}} \quad \dots (12)$$

The refined $\log \beta_{\text{pur}}$ values are shown in Table 1.

Although the possibility of enolisation of the peptide group prior to deprotonation cannot be ruled out, metal ions such as Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) will prefer to bind with the N-(peptide) atom rather than the O-(peptide) atom because of the comparatively strong ligand field that the former can provide. In the absence of X-ray data, it is however, not possible to decide which atom of the peptide group is actually bonded to the metal in the complexes. The $pK_{2\text{OH}}$ value of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2^{2-}$ ion has been found to be slightly lower than the pK_{OH} of the ligand, LH_2 , as a consequence of N-(peptide)→metal sigma bond formation. Due to such accumulation of negative charge on the metal, the subsequent deprotonation is, however, less favoured, even the possibility of some back donation through the pi-system of the peptide bond cannot be ruled out. As a matter of fact, $pK_{1\text{OH}}$ of the complex is slightly higher than the pK_{OH} of the ligand. Equilibrium concentrations of the various species involved in the complexation reaction were calculated and the distribution curves (Fig. 2) were constructed. At pH near 7.0 almost

Fig. 2. Complex distribution curve.

all the metal remain in the form of the 1 : 2 complex $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2^{2-}$ and concentration of the 1 : 1 complex $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})$ is negligible. Therefore, the assumptions made in the evaluation of the constants $K_{2\text{OH}}$ and $K_{1\text{OH}}$, that the complexation steps (4) and (5) were not overlapping with the deprotonation steps (6) and (7) are justified.

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